

Digital Twin of CERN LHC for Intervention Simulation

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Acknowledgement

Having long dreamt of contributing to a project of global significance, I am profoundly grateful for the opportunity to work on the Digital Twin of CERN's LHC for Intervention Simulation. This experience has been a dream come true, offering me the rare privilege of applying my skills to one of the most sophisticated research infrastructures in the world. The blend of innovation, collaboration, and intellectual challenge has truly enriched my professional journey.

I extend my deepest gratitude to my supervisor, Antione, and my mentors, Pablo and Jorge, whose unwavering support and expert guidance have been the cornerstones of my success. Their mentorship transcended mere technical instruction, embodying a holistic approach to professional growth. They imparted not only the intricate details of the project but also instilled in me the critical importance of adhering to best coding practices and maintaining a disciplined, analytical mindset.

Antione, Pablo and Jorge consistently demonstrated approachability and patience, offering their expertise regardless of the complexity of the challenges I encountered. Their constructive feedback and encouragement were pivotal in helping me navigate obstacles and refine my problem-solving abilities. I was always confident that any doubts or difficulties would be met with insightful and practical solutions.

This experience has been immensely rewarding, and I will always cherish the knowledge and skills I gained under their supervision. I am thankful for the opportunity to learn from such talented and supportive supervisors and mentors, and I will carry the lessons they taught me throughout my career.

1. Introduction

The project starts with the **EN-IM-PLM** team considering using a new technology in the ongoing development of a **Digital Twin: Nvidia Omniverse**.

In this project, I develop functionality using Nvidia Omniverse as a way to gauge the usefulness, quality and ease of development of this technology. In particular, the project consists of features to aid in the planning of interventions.

1.1 Digital Twins

“**Digital twins**” blur the line between the physical and the virtual. More than simulations, these virtual copies of reality incorporate real data to reshape the way we design and build, allowing us to predict real-world outcomes. A [recent workshop at CERN](#) explored the complexities of this technology and showcased its applications.

At CERN, digital twins could play a key role in high-energy physics experiments: from detector development, to designing strategies for data analytics and comparing results with theoretical models. They can be used not only to analyze and improve CERN’s infrastructure, but also to find unidentified anomalies before they arise in real life.

1.2 Nvidia Omniverse

Nvidia Omniverse is a computing platform built to enhance digital design and development by integrating 3D design, spatial computing and physics-based workflows across Nvidia tools, third-party apps and artificial intelligence (AI) services. It is used for building digital twins of products, factories, warehouses and infrastructure. It can also streamline the creation of 3D-related media for entertainment and product demonstrations, as well as enterprise media content rendered on computers, phones and extended reality (XR) devices.

The platform, launched in 2022, is available as a cloud service or a private instance running on premises. Additionally, it supports plugins and integrations for deploying

omniverse content, applications and autonomous control systems across cars, robots, building controls, equipment and medical devices.

1.3 USD Framework

Omniverse uses the Universal Scene Description framework (USD). USD is an open source framework used for interchange of 3D computer graphics data which focuses on collaboration, non-destructive editing.

USD is a high-performance extensible software platform for collaboratively constructing animated 3D scenes, designed to meet the needs of large-scale film and visual effects production.

USD enables robust interchange between digital content creation tools with its expanding set of schemas, covering domains like geometry, shading, lighting, and physics.

USD's unique composition ability provides rich and varied ways to combine assets into larger assemblies, enables collaborative workflows so that many creators can work together with ease, and more.

1.4 Intervention Planning

When changes are required in installations at CERN, from installing a new generation of magnets in the LHC to replacing power converters, there is a process of planning of the transportation and installation of the equipment. Errors in this planning can lead to expensive delays or work-arounds if, for example, the equipment to be installed doesn't fit through a corridor or if two teams are scheduled to work on the same place at the same time.

Internship Experience

1.5 Learning Omniverse

Fig: Catia model of CMS in USD format

I dedicated a significant amount of time to learning to use Omniverse during my internship. Under the guidance of my supervisors, my primary responsibility was to enable interventions and simulations within Omniverse using the 3D model of the CMS cavern.

I documented my workflow and everything I learned from the NVIDIA Omniverse documentation. In addition to explaining several topics based on my understanding, I also provided a detailed, step-by-step procedure for various processes.

1.6 Movement Animation

During my internship, I developed a **Cone Navigator Extension** for NVIDIA Omniverse. The extension allows users to calculate and visualize the shortest path between two cones in a 3D environment and animates one cone along this path. It also includes an option to spawn spheres along the path for visual reference.

Key Features:

- **Pathfinding:** Calculates the shortest path between two cones using a navigation mesh.
- **Animation:** Animates one cone along the calculated path using the timeline.
- **Sphere Spawning:** Optionally spawns spheres along the path to highlight key points.
- **User Interface:** A simple UI allows users to control pathfinding, animation, and sphere spawning.

Challenges:

- **Navigation Mesh Configuration:** Ensuring accurate pathfinding within the environment.
- **Animation Timing:** Coordinating smooth movement along the path.

Outcomes:

Working on these features enhanced my understanding of Omniverse's capabilities in pathfinding, animation, and UI design. I also gained valuable experience in writing clean, efficient code.

1.7 Lift Team Extension

The user needs to know how many people are needed to move equipment. The primary goal of this extension is to present a user-friendly interface where users can input the weight of an item, and the system will output the number of people required to lift it safely. The extension assumes a maximum safe weight limit that one person can handle, which is set at 25 kg. The extension is designed to be easy to use and integrates seamlessly with Omniverse's UI framework.

The core logic of the extension is encapsulated in the `calculate_people_required` function. This function takes the weight of the item as input and calculates the number of people required to lift the item based on the maximum weight each person can handle.

- **Single Person Handling:** If the weight is less than or equal to 25 kg, the function returns that only one person is needed.
- **Multiple Person Calculation:** If the weight exceeds 25 kg, the function calculates the total number of people required using ceiling division to ensure that the item is safely lifted without exceeding the weight limit for any individual.

Challenges

- **Handling Invalid Input:** A common challenge was ensuring that the user input was valid. This was addressed by using a try-except block to catch and handle `ValueError` exceptions if the input could not be converted to a float.
- **User Interface Design:** Designing an intuitive and straightforward UI that could be easily understood by users. The use of Omniverse's `omni.ui` components facilitated this by providing pre-built, customizable elements.

Outcome:

The "Lift Team Calculator" extension successfully provides a tool for calculating the number of people required to lift an item based on its weight. It offers a straightforward interface and reliable functionality that can be applied in various simulation scenarios within the Omniverse platform.

1.8 VR Setup in Omniverse

During my internship, I explored the potential of using Virtual Reality (VR) within NVIDIA Omniverse. Specifically, I documented the process of setting up VR using a Meta Quest 1 headset. I found out that Graphics quality of Omniverse VR scenes are better than Unity's VR rendering and it is easy to set up but it does require SteamVR.

1.9 Dynamic Agent Addition in NVIDIA Omniverse

During my internship, I developed a feature in NVIDIA Omniverse that allows users to dynamically add agents to a scene by specifying their paths. Agents are models that move around in the Scene, This functionality enhances scene management by enabling the flexible placement of agents through a user interface (UI) without requiring manual adjustments.

The goal was to create a UI that accepts path values for agents, retrieves these agents from the scene, and then displays their paths. This feature streamlines the process of agent placement and interaction within the Omniverse environment.

This feature provides a straightforward method for dynamically adding agents to a scene based on user-specified paths. By integrating this UI, users can efficiently manage and interact with agents in Omniverse, enhancing the overall flexibility and usability of the environment.

This approach not only simplifies agent management but also demonstrates practical applications of UI elements within NVIDIA Omniverse, contributing to a more interactive and user-friendly simulation experience.

Skills Developed

- Technical Skills: List and elaborate on the programming languages, tools, and technologies you became proficient in
- Python
- Omniverse
- USD, Confluence).
- Soft Skills: Discussed many improvements with Nvidia People I improved my communication, teamwork, problem-solving, and time management skills.

Bug Reports During My Internship

During my internship, I encountered and reported several bugs in NVIDIA Omniverse. These issues arose while I was working on various tasks related to animation, navigation, and scene management. Below are the details of the bugs I faced:

1. Omni.Anim.Extension Issue

- **Description:** While following the step-by-step tutorial provided in the Omniverse documentation, I encountered issues with the `Omni.Anim.Extension` module. Despite following the instructions accurately, the extension failed to function as expected.
- **Action Taken:** I reported this issue to NVIDIA, providing details about the steps followed and the unexpected behavior observed. The response I got was they will have a call with Omni.Anim Team.

2. Large Navmesh Regeneration Failure

- **Description:** I observed a problem when attempting to regenerate the navigation mesh after scaling a USD model to a larger size (10x10x10). The navigation mesh failed to generate correctly, which hindered the movement and pathfinding capabilities within the scene.

- **Action Taken:** This bug was reported to NVIDIA, highlighting the issues with navmesh generation at larger scales. It was resolved by new update.

3. Animation Graph Misplacement

- **Description:** The Animation Graph, which should have been accessible via `Add > Animation`, was instead located under `Create > Animation`. This inconsistency caused confusion and disrupted the workflow.
- **Action Taken:** I informed NVIDIA about this issue, suggesting that the documentation and UI be updated to reflect the correct location of the Animation Graph.

4. Navmesh Command Documentation Error

- **Description:** The `inav.query_navmesh_path()` command was not returning the correct object as per the documentation. Specifically, the documentation failed to mention that `path.get_points()` should be used to extract the points on the path.
- **Action Taken:** I reported this documentation error to Omniverse, recommending that the necessary corrections be made to prevent confusion for future users.

These bug reports were part of my contributions to improving the Omniverse platform during my internship. By identifying and reporting these issues, I helped ensure that the platform's functionality aligns with user expectations and documentation standards.

Future work

Future Work for the CERN Collider Digital Twin Using NVIDIA Omniverse

During my internship, I laid the groundwork for a digital twin of the CERN Collider using NVIDIA Omniverse. Future work to advance this project could focus on the following key areas:

1. **Real-Time Data Integration:** Implementing a data pipeline to stream real-time data from the Collider into Omniverse, ensuring the digital twin reflects the Collider's current state with minimal latency. This data could come from many system, including but not limited to EAM, EDMS and PLM.
2. **Enhanced 3D Environment:** Future work could focus on improving the 3D environment in Nvidia Omniverse by integrating more detailed and accurate 3D CAD models of CERN's Hadron Collider. This would create a more realistic digital twin, enhancing simulations and interventions, and supporting more efficient operations at CERN.
3. **Scalability:** Optimizing Omniverse to handle large-scale models more efficiently, focusing on performance enhancements such as LOD management and distributed computing.
4. **VR and AR Integration:** Expanding VR and AR capabilities to allow immersive, interactive experiences with the digital twin, beneficial for training and maintenance.
5. **Automated Intervention Planning:** Leveraging AI to predict maintenance needs and automatically generate optimized intervention plans, reducing downtime and risks.

6. **Collaboration Tools:** Enhancing multi-user collaboration features, including real-time synchronous editing and integrated communication tools within Omniverse.

Conclusion

During my internship, I had the opportunity to work on a variety of challenging and rewarding projects that significantly enhanced my technical and communication skills.

I am deeply grateful to my supervisors, Pablo and Jorge, for their unwavering support and guidance throughout this journey. Their willingness to teach and mentor me was invaluable. They not only provided technical advice but also motivated me to push my limits and achieve more than I thought possible. Their emphasis on good coding practices and clear communication will stay with me as I move forward in my career.

This internship has been an enriching experience, helping me grow both professionally and personally. I look forward to applying the skills and knowledge I have gained here in future projects.